

Toward Establishing Public Currency Exchange and Money Transfer Agencies to Boost National Economies in Low-Income Countries

Khaled Moustafa
The Arabic Preprint Server (ArabiXiv)
Email: khaled.moustafa@arabxiv.org

Abstract

Money transfer markets play an important role in the economic activities of many countries, particularly those with low-income and large expatriate populations. Expatriates often send money back home to support their families, providing a vital source of income for households in their countries of origin. Currently, private companies, mostly Western-based, dominate the remittance sector, charging high fees and offering unfavorable exchange rates, limiting the financial benefits for both senders and recipients. Here, I propose the establishment of government-owned currency exchange and remittance services to reduce these costs and strengthen national currency reserves in low-income countries. If one million expatriates each transfer \$100 a month, the total annual remittance would amount to \$120 million. If the number of expatriates is 5 million, the total remittances could reach \$6 billion annually. Such an initiative would not only ease the financial burden on people but also provide an opportunity for governments to reinvest parts of such funds into the national economy. Expanding the service through branches in key countries with large expatriate populations could enhance accessibility and investment, driving economic growth and ensuring greater financial sovereignty and stability.

Keywords: remittances; expatriates; government-owned service; currency exchange; economic sovereignty; financial inclusion; foreign currency reserves; money transfer market

Remittances from workers and expatriates working abroad represent a major financial resource for people in low-income regions in Africa, South America, and the Arab world where a large portion of the population works abroad. These funds often flow through private companies, primarily Western-based that dominate the money transfer market and charge high fees while offering low exchange rates. Consequently, the stakeholders often bear the brunt of these high transaction costs.

Gap in the Market

The absence of government-supported companies offering affordable remittance services underscores a major market gap. This situation presents an opportunity for governments to establish state-owned currency exchange and remittance services. By doing so, they could recover some of the profits currently absorbed by private companies and reinvest the gathered funds into the national economy.

Establishing a Government-Owned Currency Exchange and Remittance Service

Given the vast volume of remittances globally, government-backed currency exchange services could offer several benefits, including:

- **Boosting national economies:** Large expatriate populations could generate substantial remittance volumes, creating investment opportunities. For instance, 10 million expatriates sending \$100 monthly would amount to \$12 billion annually in remittances, providing an important source of funding for essential goods and development projects.
- **Enhancing foreign currency reserves:** A state-run remittance service would allow governments to capture a larger share of these funds, contributing to national currency reserves. These reserves could be used to import necessary goods and services or finance development projects.
- **Lowering money transfer costs:** Governments could offer more affordable and efficient remittance services by bypassing private companies, alleviating the financial burden on expatriate and their families through fairer exchange rates and lower transfer fee.
- **Promoting economic sovereignty:** Governments could set up branches in countries with large expatriate populations or utilize embassies and consulates as money sending points, enhancing accessibility and security of remittance transactions. Such initiatives would enable governments to benefit from a vital financial market, redirecting funds back into national economies, thus promoting economic stability and reducing dependency on external financial systems.

Finally, creating government-owned currency exchange and remittance agencies would be a strategic move for many developing countries, particularly those with high numbers of expatriates working abroad. This initiative would not only benefit expatriate by offering lower fees and fairer exchange rates but also strengthen national economies by capturing important shares of the remittance market. In turn, this would enhance national currency reserves and contribute to long-term economic growth.